

A Review of Soil Contamination and Remediation on Basis of Case Studies

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Abstract:

Soil contamination has increased over the past few decades, mainly due to petroleum hydrocarbons, heavy metals, pesticides application, industrial wastes, and human activities. Suitable and standardized monitoring and remediation strategies are required to minimize soil contamination. In this sense, in the most recent decade, there has been a developing innovative technology on the usage of residues and waste materials, originating from various industries, many remediation innovations (Chemical degradation, photo- degradation) and bioremediation to clean polluted soils. The purpose of this article is to collect contributions from outstanding researches and experts involved in various fields of soil contamination and soil degradation with some case studies to highlights and future developments in the context of contaminated soil monitoring and remediation strategies. The article is planned into six topics containing an introduction, soil pollution, types and sources of soil pollution, soil contamination and degradation, soil remediation and some case studies. I hope that the composed data will be beneficial to soil contamination researchers, (e.g., geologists, engineers, and biologists to get an overview of soil contamination and degradation

Keywords: Soil Contamination-Soil Degradation- Soil Remediation- Case Study

1. Introduction:

Soil can be characterized the assemblage of natural bodies attending part of the Earth's surface that is able for supporting plant development and that has properties effect on the atmosphere and living organisms following up on parent material, as depend upon geography, over timeframes. Soil is the composition of minerals, inorganic, organic, solid, gases, liquid, and living organisms.

Abiotic and biotic material is present in the soil, size of mineral particles (clay, silt, salt, and organic matter) are different in abiotic. On the other hand plants, animals and micro-organisms they all are different in size, different in numbers, different in habits, different in the life cycle, different in the food source. Therefore soil has physical chemical and biological properties which respond to changes. Complicated relation between organisms and abiotic component have a crucial role in soil creation, organic matters impart, nutrients cycling and some contaminants degradation. Naturally, soil plays out a few environmental services which were a divide into four categories: human benefit, quality of the environment, biodiversity, and fertility and sustainability. Some major behavior of soil such as the production of food and biomass, territory for a mixture of organisms, filtering, and settlement of water, impart of organic matters and cycling of nutrients, storage of carbon and support of human life. If we discuss urbanization for developing soil contribute the main role because in this process want also parks and garden which add to the conservation of biodiversity and play a specific role in the environment. Soil connected with another ecosystem such as atmosphere, biosphere, and hydrosphere, consequently atmosphere and water quality directly depends on soil conditions and therefore, human or animal health dependent on soil quality. Peoples now recognized that the soil is basic or fundamental protection of environmental quality at worldwide, the soil has the buffering capacity give to water quality since the capability of the sink for contaminated metal can have a major role in controlling the pollution in a world environment. For all these logic soil is viewed as a fundamental asset, and because of its moderate arrangement, it tends to be thought about nonrenewable. Besides, it has impacts on natural, financial, what's more, social exercises. Soil pollution is a major issue of the world because human life directly or indirectly connected with soil,

2. Soil pollution:

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When the peoples of the world introduced chemicals, harmful matters, and toxic substance, after this, they dump waste materials directly or indirectly in soil that reason soil and water destroy or polluted ecosystem. Effect of pollution of soil directly link with living organisms (human and animals) Soil pollution is frequently considered as a concealed threat or danger because it is kind of contamination (pollution) that's not seen easily with eyes, soil pollution directly effected on food chain and damage health of living organisms[]Pollution of soil increased over the last decades, it is risk or danger for human health and ecological system Human activities are the main cause of soil contamination, they use (organic and inorganic) chemical which can be gotten from anthropogenic-related exercises, or normally happening in soil. Scanning of soil quality is very difficult due to the lake of well-stated scanning variable and indicators. On the other hand, the world wants sustainability and fertility of soil increased due to population increase, therefore soil pollution is a very important topic due to all issues.

Soil pollution majorly affects the whole planet and it will assume an extensive job in the prosperity of future generation. All the better we can do now is actualize measures to hinder the contamination and tidy up dirtied regions where conceivable. Doing nothing will just enable the pollution to advance to a point where our soil turns into the reason for significant wellbeing scourges (major health infectious).furthermore next 40 years human population increase expected to grow 2 billion, With that being the situation, it is of most extreme significance that the dirt stays in politeness so as to encourage the population. [1-6]

2.1 Types of soil pollution:

The fundamental pollutants of the soil are the natural operators and a portion of the human exercises. Soil pollutants are for the most part results of soil toxins that sully the dirt. Human exercises that dirty the dirt range from farming practices that plague the harvests with pesticide synthetic compounds to urban or modern squanders or radioactive discharges that defile the dirt with different poisonous substances.

- a) Biological agents
- b) Urban waste
- c) Radioactive pollutants
- d) Industrial waste
- e) Agriculture pesticides

2.2 Causes of soil pollution:

There are many causes of soil pollution present in previous literature but in the current study, we explained the major causes of soil pollution. For simplicity of reference, they are commonly divided into two parts such as Anthropogenic (man-made) and natural cause.

Human made or man-made soil pollution causes:

Anthropogenic (man-made) soil pollution starts in a few sorts of procedures, some industrial and some unplanned. Human-caused soil pollution can work related to normal procedures to build the poisonous sullyng levels in the soil.

- a) Spills and leaks: storage of chemicals or transport of chemical (spills and leaks)
- b) Mining of (coal, gold, silver, petrol): in the processing of raw material and crushing of materials, for example, heavy metals, discharging toxic substance
- c) Construction activities: urban area construction of new building and roads, generated a huge amount of pollutant
- d) Agricultural work: including the dispersion of herbicides, pesticides as well as insecticides and fertilizers.
- e) Dumping: illegal dumping of a chemical substance in soil

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- f) Foundry: manufacturing process that includes furnace Or other process make a reason for the diffusion of pollutant in the environment
- g) Storage of waste: waste material used for landfilling and pollutant went in groundwater or generated polluted vapors
- h) Transportation activity: discharging harmful vehicle emanations

3. Natural pollutants:

Aside from the uncommon situations when a characteristic collection of synthetic concoctions prompts soil pollution, normal procedures may likewise have an effect on the human discharged harmful synthetics into the soil, generally speaking diminishing or expanding the toxin harmfulness or potentially the dimension of tainting of the dirt. This is conceivable because of the perplexing soil condition, including the nearness of different synthetic compounds and regular conditions which may connect with the discharged poisons.

3.1 Natural processes noted to soil pollution:

- a) **Natural growth:** during natural growth of compound in soil expected to unbalance between atmospheric impeachment and discharge or go away with precipitation water
- b) **Natural production:** in the soil, some natural production depends upon certain environmental conditions
- c) **Sewer line leakage:** in to belowground eg adding chlorine which generated triholomethanes

4. Soil contamination:

The solid waste material gets or attended a wide range of toxic metals or heavy metals such as Arsenic (As), cadmium (cd), chromium (cr), copper (cu), Mercury (hg), lead (pb), selenium (se) and zinc. The entrance of soil narrow metals also affected the food chain that means we can say food chain depend on the soil because uptake amount of metals by plant and animal absorbed. Soil contamination is mainly caused by human activity, in developed countries of health authorities are becoming progressively disturbed for human are affected by soil contaminations. Heavy metals or toxic metals are dumping in the soil this process is very haram full for the worldwide environment, if we see history or past some decades heavy metal or toxic metals affected the world environment because of its poisoning, human health received dangerous disease. Many examples or cases available in the world history such as in Japan 1950s (Minamata disease) founded and scientist did investigate from which source Minamata disease came, in the end, they found fish containing methyl mercuric compound because soil waste dumped in rivers.

Recently reported the high concentration of heavy metals such as Arsenic, cadmium, copper, and zinc in soil and groundwater in the Asian countries for example in China, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India human affected by the high amount of AS(arsenic) in soil or water and these peoples potential danger from AS poisoning. more use of fertilizer in New Zealand and Australia soil is contaminated with a high value of cadmium (cd) these contaminants enter in the food chain, affecting the meat production to over all the world market. Similarly, in urbanization, we use horticulture site for beauty and food but they contain a lot of amount of heavy metals such as CU, AS and Pb in soil because they use a high quantity of fungicide and herbicides that are wealthy in heavy metals. Unlike organic pollutants, metals don't undergo microbial or chemical degradation and these pollutants are present for a long time after their introduction.

4.2 Sources of contamination:

In earthly environments, the soil is the fundamental vault of synthetic contaminants. In like manner in aquatic frameworks, the silt serves as a definitive sink for these chemicals. Contaminant reaches in the soil through both pedogenic and anthropogenic forms. Most heavy or toxic metals happen normally in soil parent materials, mostly in structures that are not promptly bioavailable for plant take-up. Dissimilar to pedogenic inputs, heavy or toxic metals included through anthropogenic exercises commonly have a high bioavailability through anthropogenic exercises

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ordinarily have a high bioavailability [Anthropogenic exercises, basically connected with industrial procedures, manufacturing, the transfer of residential and modern waste materials, and the use of P fertilizer are the real wellspring of metal advancement in soils [9-11]

Figure. (a). The graph shows a breakdown of the main sources causing soil contamination in Europe as % of the number of sites where preliminary investigations have been completed (European Environmental Bureau) [41]

There are two main sources of heavy metals Geogenic and Anthropogenic.

a) Geogenic:

The greater part of the substantial metal happen in nature, the real source of which is enduring of soil parent materials including volcanic what's more, sedimentary shakes, and coal. Most of As is gotten from the geogenic beginning. For instance, coal is evaluated to discharge 45,000 huge amounts of As every year, while human exercises discharge roughly 50,000 tons. The As a substance of igneous rocks differs broadly (up to 100 mg/kg); the normal substance is 2– 3 mg/kg. Sedimentary rocks likewise change in their As a substance, from little sums in limestone and sandstone up to 15,000 mg/kg in some manganese minerals. But the anthropogenic As the source is progressively getting to be significant, freshly cases of huge contamination (As) of groundwater in many countries such as Russia, China, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India, transported by the river. Essentially, seleniferous soils found in the zones of Se-rich rocks,

For example, dark shale's, carbonaceous limestones, carbonaceous cherts, mudstones, and seleniferous coal are a noteworthy wellspring of Se contribution to the soil. Additionally, irrigation of Se-rich groundwater had appeared to pollute irrigation channel water and surface waters in the San Joaquin Valley, California (United States), and in Punjab, India. Volcanic and geological exercises activate mercury from profound supplies in the earth to the air. Yearly discharge of mercury Hg from worldwide mercuriferous belts, the zone along plate structural counting western North America, focal Europe, and southern China was evaluated up to 500 Mg/year.

b) Anthropogenic:

Anthropogenic activities are human made activates these exercises principally connected with the industrial process, manufacturing and household waste or domestic disposal and industrial waste, these wastes are rich in heavy metal, solid waste material are in dumped in soil.

Environment contamination from Pb-based oil was a noteworthy issue in many countries where there was no imperative on the utilization of fuel. While biosolids are the major wellspring of heavy metal contributions to Europe and North America, P fertilizers are viewed as the major source of heavy metal input, particularly Cd, in Australia and New Zealand. Phosphate compounds contain a range of metal. Cadmium (cd) pollution of agriculture soils is of specific concern since it achieves the food chain through ordinary utilization of cadmium-containing P fertilizer. The Cd in most P fertilizer begins

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for the most part from the phosphate rocks (PRs) utilized for assembling P fertilizer. Many countries of the world have planned limit levels for Cd and other heavy metals gathering in soils because of the utilization of metropolitan biosolids, such breaking points have not been built up from compost use. Enormous amounts of Cu are utilized in horticulture, agriculture, cultivation and animal industry, in numerous plans of Cu containing fungicides, for example, copper oxychloride and 'Bordeaux' blend, and as a development advertiser in piggery and poultry units.

Aggregation of Cu in farming soils coming about because of constant utilization of Cu fungicides and biosolids application has been revealed in many countries. One of the significant results of unnecessary gathering of Cu in soils is its poisonous quality to plants furthermore, microbial networks, In New Zealand around 6400 and 1600 tons of tannery and timber Treatment effluents, separately, are created every year, and these effluents are viewed as the significant sources of Cr pollutant into environment situations. Chromium is utilized as Cr (III) in the tannery business and as Cr (VI) in the timber treatment industry. Chromate is exceedingly dangerous and cancer-causing notwithstanding when present in extremely low focus on water. Enormous scale utilization of Cu– Cr– As (CCA) regarded timber as a fence post and in vineyards can likewise result in the arrival of Cu, Cr, and As to soil condition [12-31]

4.3 Soil degradation:

See how the nature of soil decreases and what causes this decay. Soil degradation is the decrease in soil condition brought about by its ill-advised use or poor administration, typically for agriculture, modern or urban purposes. It is a genuine ecological issue. Soils are a basic normal asset, and reason for all living life. Keeping away from soil degradation is pivotal to our prosperity [32-35]. Soil degradation is an undefined term recommending that the limit of soil to perform chosen indicated services, for example, crop-growing, has been decreased. The idea appears to be fairly basic, yet measuring degradation has been exceptionally testing and makes vulnerability related with evaluating land debasement endeavors, a worldwide assessment of soil or land degradation requires examining or potentially assessment approach and a land debasement metric that addresses issues and interests for various gatherings. Testing required for a quantitatively defensible assessment shifts between various scenes and soil qualities under investigation. For instance, inside a given field, slope tops or side slants might be degraded from soil erosion, while level zones might be unaltered or even improved from eroded topsoil removal. A solitary incentive to depict change over different broadly varying spatial conditions in little zones has various understanding difficulties. The worldly inspecting period required to protectively portray rate of soil change, or power of progress, might be different decades, Regardless of different difficulties, different endeavors to address and evaluate soil degradation at the worldwide scale exist in the writing. [36-37]

5. Soil remediation:

Soil washing is another name of soil remediation, the removal of contaminants from the soil is called soil remediation. Growing of agriculture for the human they want healthy soil because if we have healthy soil that means we have healthy groundwater and healthy air.

When a requirement for soil remediation is perceived, the best accessible innovation is chosen by the nature, poisonous quality, and origin of the contaminant, the present and potential danger identified with the level of pollution, the concoction and physical attributes of the soil, the land use, the time accessible for remediation, the network acknowledgment, and a money saving advantage examination. These various criteria differ broadly in the innovations depicted previously. The advancement of minimal effort, low-input advances, driven in the industrialized country by financial advantages, is additionally fundamental to handle the remediation of contaminated soils in developing countries. Some types or technologies depicted in this article are settled, while others are as yet being created. Due to consistently expanding open worry for the dangers presented by soil contamination, it is normal that a bigger number of innovations will be accessible in the future. [38-40]

There is various type of soil remediation, each utilizing a particular method for expelling contaminants from soil.

- a) Thermal Soil Remediation
- b) Encapsulation
- c) Air Sparging
- d) Bioremediation

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Figure. (b) .The graph shows remediation technologies applied in the surveyed countries as percentages of a number of sites per type of treatment -European Environmental Bureau [41].

a) Thermal soil remediation: it is the type of soil remediation that remove heavy or toxic metals from the soil with the help of high temperature, this procedure is normally saved for soil that has been polluted with contaminated water or by hydrocarbon compound, for example, oil or other oil based commodities. Ordinarily, we use an oven for heating. thermal remediation offers more noteworthy command over operational parameters (time, temperature) and is utilized when objectives incorporate I) quick removal of contaminants; ii) severe adherence to a cleanup objective, requiring high quality; and iii) decrease of long term risk. thermal remediation is a classification of procedures that utilization of heat I) upgrade the mobility of contaminants (e.g., steam/sight-seeing injection); ii) separate contaminants from soil particles (e.g., warm desorption, microwave warming); iii) change contaminants into less psionic byproduct (e.g., pyrolysis); IV) damage contaminants (e.g., cremation, seething); or v) immobilize contaminants [41-43]While thermal treatment can be quicker and more dependable than some different techniques, it normally requires more framework and apparatus, bringing about greater expenses. Also, soil warming is known to influence various soil properties, and the modification of these properties may direct land utilize following remediation. The degree of this adjustment might be a significant factor in the usage of warm remediation, the same number of professionals are blending remediation with ensuing recovery or reclamation endeavors. So, understanding the impacts of thermal remediation on soil properties is basic data in the basic leadership process that happens toward the start of a project. Broad research has been led relating to the advancement of these systems and the materialness over a scope of circumstances. Associating the impacts of thermal remediation on soil work is crucial in the successive recovery or restoration process.

Soil work, in this survey, is comprehended as the capacity of the soil to play out the accompanying capacities: I) fill in as reasonable natural surroundings equipped for continuing biodiversity; ii) give structure and an asset vehicle for biomass production; iii) store and filter, groundwater resources; iv) detoxify, degrade and handle wastes through cycling of nutrients and continuing resources storage; v) soil act as a very important role for human development; and vi) give social and anthropological centrality, Deciding the

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general impact of soil heating on soil capacities can't be legitimately estimated in light of the fact that those capacities are represented by the dynamic connections of a wide range of soil properties and ecological procedures. In any case, recognizing changes to explicit soil properties is profitable in making presumptions about how overall soil capacity will be influenced by heating.

- b) Encapsulation:** The procedure of encapsulation does not filter pollutant from soil but it isolates them. This should be possible from multiple ways, yet a standout amongst the most well-known ways of mixing contaminated soil with lime, concrete, and cement, prompting keeping the contaminants from spreading to clean soil. However it may, this technique blocks utilizing the soil for development. Encapsulating polluted material can be a powerful innovation for isolating contaminants and possibly a reasonable option for securing human health and the ecosystem when expulsion and off-site disposal may not be financially effective as well as functional. Essential destinations for the plan and development of an encapsulation cell incorporate [44]
- c) Air sparging:** In air sparging, huge volumes of air are injected into a contaminated soil stratum to drive the natural vapors outwards where they are commonly treated via carbon separating. The genuine time the procedure takes in treatment relies on different factors, for example, the intensity of the hydrocarbon contamination, the concentration of pollutant, pH factor of the soil, and porousness of the soil. This application is very effective for the volatile compounds that present in soil because peoples store the petroleum compounds in an underground tank and this activity pollute soil, lighter gasoline can remove from the soil easily with the help of air sparging. Air Sparging is less pertinent to diesel fuel and kerosene[45]
- d) Bioremediation:** Contaminated soil treated with biological methods for remove pollutant from soil this is called bioremediation, it is very cheap and easy type of soil remediation, the procedure employments bacterium (Anaerobic species and Aerobic), especially focused to devour and separate hydrocarbons and different contaminations in soil, biological mechanism instead of a mechanical technique for separating or removing pollutant from soil. Bioremediation, for the most part, alludes to the breakdown of in the end bringing about the development of carbon do methane. Inorganic mixes are not degraded, however, changed into a compound having less versatility or cases, the bioremediation forms include a part atomic site. Complete and quick biodegradation just explicit natural conditions, yet in addition ch the organism At the temperature 70degree f this application give good result for removing pollutants from soil [46-47]

6. CASE STUDY:

Many laboratories and glasshouse tests have inspected the impacts of different assembling and immobilizing revisions in the change and bioavailability of heavy metal in soils, however, a narrow number of studies have analyzed the potential estimation of these alterations in the remediation of metal defiled soils under field conditions. In this segment, chose field explores in which the estimation of a portion of the soil amendment in the remediation of different polluted sites will be accounted for.

The stock of field probes phytostabilization and immobilization of metal in Europe are outlined by Vangronsveld et al. By 2009, there were 27 field cases in 10 European nations recorded in logical productions. Soil alterations, for example, alumina silicates and liming materials (gravel sludge, zeolites, lime, limestone, sugar beet), organic materials(compost, biosolid compost, peats, chicken manure)and oxides (iron, red mud, iron girt)were used to immobilization of heavy metals from polluted soil [48]

Some study case about remediation of soil:

1. Cadmium polluted paddy soil washing process
2. Copper and lead were immobilized in mine spoil
3. Immobilization of Ar (arsenic element) in polluted soil with wood impregnations
4. immobilization of lead in smelter buildup

1. Cadmium polluted paddy soil washing process:

Soil washing is customarily performed ex situ utilizing suitable equipment, in which separating reagents are utilized to expel heavy metal from the soil into aqueous solution. The in situ soil washing is generally called "soil flushing"; thusly, the word "soil washing" is reliably utilized in this area to maintain a strategic distance from perplexity. The soil washing systems offer an incredible preferred position of high Cd-removal proficiency for polluted soils. This method has been viewed as hard to apply straightforwardly to agriculture land since wastewater depleted amid the procedure of soil washing may contaminate encompassing conditions, for example, farming channels, neighboring agricultural fields, and groundwater. However paddy fields have an impenetrable hardpan just beneath the subsurface layer, which prevents vertical development of water, the washed solution remains in the surface soil and does not enter into subsoil layers and groundwater. Thus, an in situ innovation of soil washing ought to be used completely to exploit. [49-51]

6.2 Copper and lead was immobilized in mine spoil:

Acidic seepage generation from sulfide containing mine wastes causes soil fermentation and contaminant filtering. A half ton acid soil gathered from a Cu metal transshipment station in the north of Sweden was stabilized with coal fly ash and peat, and along with untreated soil, set in open air lysimeters. The fundamental point of the examination was to kill soil acidity and decrease filtering of Cu and Pb. Leachates were gathered for a long time. Amid the initial two years, the draining of Cu and Pb diminished fundamentally in the treated soil while soil pH stayed neutral, the revision mix additionally encouraged soil recovery through expanded microbial biomass and respiration, soil enzyme action, and, continued plant development. Further breaks down of leachates demonstrated that the immobilizing impact has been supported amid the whole ten-years testing period. The coal fly ash was display long term neutralization capacity, as pH of the treated soil stayed impartial even following ten years.[52]

6.3 Immobilization of Ar (arsenic element) in polluted soil with wood impregnations:

The capacity of Fe-containing alterations to effectively immobilize As in soil is notable. In any case, Fe will, in general, immobilize unintended components, for example, nutrient, which further declines the soil capacity to support vegetative growth and microbial capacities. The fertility of soil can improve with the use of nutrient rich mechanical deposit, kumpiene scientist do research in laboratory for two years where he saw

As-polluted soil was treated with Fe alone and in the mix with coal fly ash, biosolids from sewage slime, peat, or gypsum. The point of this examination was to decide As polluted soil cloud be used in construction work on the upper layer of land, The As portability and soil synthetic and biochemical properties were checked for a long time utilizing 2 m sections repeating the assurance/vegetation layer of the landfill spread.[53-54]

6.4 Immobilization of lead in smelter buildup:

IINERT(in place inactivation and natural ecological restoration technologies) was attempted field study Action Team aimed at developing and validating in situ techniques as viable technologies for eliminating the hazards of Pb(lead) in soils and surficial materials. Field plot shows were set up in a private setting nearby a Pb lead smelter, which worked from the 1880s until its shutting in the late 1960s at Joplin, MO, USA. The alterations utilized in the investigation were grouped into three classes at different fixations: P just (triple superphosphate, rock phosphate, and phosphoric acidic), P and Fe (iron rich containing) and triple super P, and P and (biosolids and TSP). Tests were gathered at 3, 18, and 32 months after treatment, assessed for Pb immobilization as a component of time and dissected by in vivo creature nourishing, in vitro substance extraction, and soil design by means of spectroscopic and extraction strategies.[55-56].

Conclusion:

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Quick development or industrialization during the last decades has produced a large amount of pollution in the environment; some activities of nature also affected the earth ecosystem. The world has many types of threats but the most critical risk is to have soil pollution because soil made the earth and ecosystem of land depending on the soil. Soil contamination and degradation are increasing day by day. It has adversely impacted on the soil as well as human health, so, it is very important to learn about this and solve a major problem. In the world, all living things are depended on soil but from last decades soil was contaminated by human activities and pollute the environment of earth, present study explain contamination, types of contamination and resources of contamination. So, we recommend focussing minimizing soil contamination to save our earth and minimize the causes that are behind soil contamination.

References:

- i. Anabela Cachada (Soil and Pollution: An Introduction to the Main Issues) <http://www.eschooltoday.com>
- ii. www.conservationinstitute.org
- iii. N. Brady, R. Weil, *The Nature and Properties of Soils, fourteenth ed.*, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ, 2008.
- iv. J. Bone, M. Head, D. Barraclough, M. Archer, C. Scheib, D. Flight, N. Voulvoulis, *Soil quality assessment under emerging regulatory requirements*, *Environ. Int.* 36 (2010) 609622.
- v. D.L. Karlen, M.J. Mausbach, J.W. Doran, R.G. Cline, R.F. Harris, G.E. Schuman, *Soil quality: a concept, definition, and framework for evaluation (a guest editorial)*, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J* 61 (1997)
- vi. D.C. Adriano, *Trace Elements in Terrestrial Environments: Biogeochemistry, Bioavailability and Risks of Metals, second ed.*, Springer, New York, 2001
- vii. B. Knopf, H. König, *Biomethylation of Heavy Metals in Soil and Terrestrial Invertebrates: Soil Heavy Metals*, Springer, Berlin/Heidelberg, 2010, pp.315–328
- viii. S. Bhattacharya, K. Gupta, S. Debnath, U.C. Ghosh, D. Chattopadhyay, A. Mukhopadhyay, *Arsenic bioaccumulation in rice and edible plants and subsequent transmission through food chain in Bengal basin: a review of the perspectives for environmental health*, *Toxicol. Environ. Chem.* 94 (2012) 429–441
- ix. P. Loganathan, M.J. Hedley, N.D. Grace, *Pasture soils contaminated with fertilizer derived cadmium and fluoride: livestock effects*, *Rev. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 192 (2008) 29–66
- x. U. Pietrzak, N. Uren, *Remedial options for copper-contaminated vineyard soils*, *Soil Res.* 49 (2011) 44–55
- xi. D.C. Adriano, W.W. Wenzel, J. Vangronsveld, N.S. Bolan, *Role of assisted natural remediation in environmental cleanup*, *Geoderma* 122 (2004) 121–142
- xii. *Soil and Land Pollution (J.F. Artiola, J.L. Walworth, S.A. Musil and M.A. Crimmins)*
- xiii. N.S. Bolan, D.C. Adriano, R. Naidu, *Role of phosphorus in (im)mobilization and bioavailability of heavy metals in the soil–plant system*, *Rev. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 177 (2003) 1–44
- xiv. J.N. Galloway, J.D. Thornton, S.A. Norton, H.I. Volchok, R.A.N. McLean, *Tracemetals in atmospheric deposition – a review and assessment*, *Atmos. Environ.* 16 (1982) 1677–1700
- xv. C.W. Gray, R.G. McLaren, A.H.C. Roberts, *Atmospheric accessions of heavy metals to some New Zealand pastoral soils*, *Sci. Total Environ.* 305 (2003) 105–11
- xvi. J.E. Ferguson, J. Gavis, *A review of the arsenic cycle in natural waters*, *Water Res.* 6 (1972) 1259–1274
- xvii. S. Mahimairaja, N.S. Bolan, D. Adriano, B. Robinson, *Arsenic contamination and its risk management in complex environmental settings*, *Adv. Agron.* 86(2005) 1–82.
- xviii. H. Yan-Chu, *Arsenic distribution in soils*, in: J.O. Nriagu (Ed.), *Arsenic in the Environment: Part I. Cycling and Characterization*, John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1994, pp. 17–49
- xix. G. Yu, D. Sun, Y. Zheng, *Health effects of exposure to natural arsenic in groundwater and coal in China: an overview of occurrence*, *Environ. Health Perspect.* 115 (2007) 636–642
- xx. M.A. Armienta, R. Rodriguez, O. Cruz, *Arsenic content in hair of people exposed*

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- xxii. *to natural arsenic polluted groundwater at Zimapan, Mexico, Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 59 (1997) 583–589.
- xxiii. L.M. Del Razo, M.A. Arellano, M.E. Cebrian, *The oxidation states of arsenic in well-water from a chronic arsenicism area in northern Mexico, Environ. Pollut.* 64 (1990) 143–153
- xxiv. K.S. Dhillon, S.K. Dhillon, *Quality of underground water and its contribution towards selenium enrichment of the soil–plant system for a seleniferous region of northwest India, J. Hydrol.* 272 (2003) 120–130
- xxv. W.T. Frankenberger Jr., M. Arshad, *Bioremediation of selenium contaminated sediments and water, Biofactors* 14 (2001) 241–254
- xxvi. J.C. Varekamp, P.R. Buseck, *Global mercury flux from volcanic and geothermal sources, Appl. Geochem.* 1 (1986) 65–73
- xxvii. J. Fenger, *Air pollution in the last 50 years – from local to global, Atmos. Environ.* 43 (2009) 13–22
- xxviii. R.J. Haynes, G. Murtaza, R. Naidu, *Inorganic and organic constituents and contaminants in biosolids: implications for land application, Adv. Agron.* 104 (2009) 165–267
- xxix. M.J. McLaughlin, K.G. Tiller, R. Naidu, D.P. Stevens, *Review: the behavior and environmental impact of contaminants in fertilizers, Aust. J. Soil Res.* 34 (1996) 1–54
- xxx. R.A. Wuana, F.E. Okieimen, *Heavy metals in contaminated soils: a review of sources, chemistry, risks and best available strategies for remediation, ISRN Ecol.* 2011 (2011) 1–20
- xxxi. A.M. Wightwick, S.A. Salzman, S.M. Reichman, G. Allinson, N.W. Menzies,
- xxxii. *Effects of copper fungicide residues on the microbial function of vineyard soils, Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 20 (2013) 1574–1585.
- xxxiii. D.A. Heemsbergen, M.J. McLaughlin, M. Whatmuff, M.S.J. Warne, K. Broos, M.J. Bell, D. Nash, G. Barry, D. Pritchard, N. Penney, *Bioavailability of zinc and copper in biosolids compared to their soluble salts, Environ. Pollut.* 158 (2010) 1907–1915.
- xxxiv. A.M. Wightwick, S.A. Salzman, S.M. Reichman, G. Allinson, N.W. Menzies, *Inter-regional variability in environmental availability of fungicide derived copper in vineyard soils: an Australian case study, J. Agric. Food Chem.* 58(2010) 449–457
- xxxv. Soil Jerry L. Hatfield, ... Richard M. Cruse, in *Advances in Agronomy*, 2017
- xxxvi. www.environment.nsw.gov.au/topics/land-and-soil/soil-degradation
- xxxvii. *REMEDIATION OF POLLUTED SOILS* (E. Lombi, R.E. Hamon, in *Encyclopedia of Soils in the Environment*, 2005)
- xxxviii. www.spokaneenvironmental.com
- xxxix. *FRTR (Federal Remediation Technologies Roundtable), 2017. Remediation Technologies Screening Matrix and Reference Guide, Version 4.0.* <https://frtr.gov/matrix2/section1/toc.html>. (Accessed 28 June 2017).
- xl. Khan, F., Husain, T., Hejazi, R., 2004. *An overview and analysis of site remediation technologies. J. Environ. Manag.* 71, 95e122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2004.02.003>
- xli. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/remediation-technologies>
- xlii. Vidonish, J.E., Zygourakis, K., Masiello, C.A., Sabadell, G., Alvarez, P.J.J., 2016b. *Thermal treatment of hydrocarbon-impacted soils: a review of technology innovation for sustainable remediation. Engineering* 2, 426e437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eng.2016.04.005>.
- xliii. Stefan Demcak, Magdalena Balintova 2015 (*Overview of chosen techniques and methods for soils remediation*)
- xliv. R.L Johnson et al. (1993). *An Overview of In Situ Air Sparging. Groundwater Monitoring & Remediation.* Vol. 13 (Is. 4). 127-135. DOI: 10.1111/j.1745-6592.1993.tb00456.x
- xlv. K.T. Jarvinen, E.S. Melin, and J.A. Puhakka. (1994). *High-rate bioremediation of chlorophenol contaminated groundwater at low temperatures. Environmental Science & Technology.* Vol. 28, 2387-2392.

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- xlvi. R.E. Hoepfel, R.E. Hinchee. (1994). Enhanced biodegradation for on-site remediation of contaminated soils and groundwater. In: *Hazardous Waste Site Soil Remediation: Theory and Application of Innovative Technologies*. D.J. Wilson and A.N. Clarke (eds). New York, NY: M.Dekker.
- xlvii. J. Vangronsveld, R. Herzig, N. Weyens, J. Boulet, K. Adriaensen, A. Ruttens, T. Thewys, A. Vassilev, E. Meers, E. Nehnevajova, D. Van der Lelie, M. Mench, Phytoremediation of contaminated soils and groundwater: lessons from the field, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 16 (2009) 765–794.
- xlviii. H.A. Elliott, L.M. Herzig, Oxalate extraction of Pb and Zn from polluted soils:
i. solubility limitations, *J. Soil Contam.* 8 (1999) 105–116
- xlix. T. Makino, K. Sugahara, Y. Sakurai, H. Takano, T. Kamiya, K. Sasaki, T. Itou, N. Sekiya, Remediation of cadmium contamination in paddy soils by washing with chemicals: selection of washing chemicals, *Environ. Pollut.* 144 (2006) 2–10.
- l. T. Makino, T. Kamiya, H. Takano, T. Itou, N. Sekiya, K. Sasaki, Y. Sugahara, Y. Maejima, Remediation of cadmium-contaminated paddy soils by washing with calcium chloride: verification of on-site washing, *Environ. Pollut.* 147(2007) 112–119.
- li. L.A. Oste, J. Dolfig, W.C. Ma, T.M. Lexmond, Effect of beringite on cadmium and zinc uptake by plants and earthworms: more than a liming effect? *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 20 (2001) 1339–1345
- lii. J. Kumpiene, P. Desogus, S. Schulenburg, M. Arenella, G. Renella, E. Brännvall, A. Lagerkvist, L. Andreas, R. Sjöblom, Utilisation of chemically stabilized arsenic-contaminated soil in a landfill cover, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* (2013), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11356-013-1818-3>
- liii. A. Ruttens, M. Mench, J.V. Colpaert, J. Boisson, R. Carleer, J. Vangronsveld, Phytostabilization of a metal contaminated sandy soil. I: Influence of compost and/or inorganic metal immobilizing soil amendments on phytotoxicity and plant availability of metals, *Environ. Pollut.* 144 (2006) 524–532.
- liv. J.A. Ryan, K.G. Scheckel, W.R. Berti, S.L. Brown, S.W. Casteel, R.L. Chaney, J. Hallfrisch, M. Doolan, P. Grevatt, M. Maddaloni, D. Mosby, Reducing children's risk from lead in soil, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 38 (2004) 18A–24A
- lv. K.G. Scheckel, J.A. Ryan, Spectroscopic speciation and quantification of lead in phosphate-amended soils, *J. Environ. Qual.* 33 (2004) 1288–1295.